

SMARTWIN Data Management Plan

Version 1

Description

This Data Management Plan (DMP) defines how the outputs and research data generated in the project ***Design and demonstration of a translucent photovoltaic smart window for building-integrated photovoltaics (SMARTWIN)*** will be created, documented, preserved, and managed throughout their lifecycle, ensuring responsible management of all project data in line with best open science practices and FAIR principles.

Based on a collaboration between **Instituto de Energía Solar - UPM** and **IMDEA Nanociencia**, the SMARTWIN project aims to evaluate, develop, and manufacture an innovative translucent photovoltaic smart window capable of blocking direct sunlight, generating clean electricity, and transmitting diffuse light to improve building energy efficiency.

This multidisciplinary research produces data in diverse fields, such as optical, electrical, thermal, and mechanical, which implies managing heterogeneous information. This DMP establishes instructions on how to ensure that datasets are findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable in accordance with the FAIR principles. To support this, an official SMARTWIN community in Zenodo has been established to guarantee that all datasets remain openly available.

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AGENCIA ESTATAL DE INVESTIGACIÓN

Grant

Proyectos de Transición Ecológica y Transición Digital.

Acronym: SMARTWIN.

Reference: TED2021-130920B-C21.

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: SMARTWIN Data Management Plan

Description: This Data Management Plan (DMP) defines the procedures for managing the datasets generated in the *Design and demonstration of a translucent photovoltaic smart window for building-integrated photovoltaics (SMARTWIN)*, which seeks to develop an innovative translucent photovoltaic smart window capable of blocking direct sunlight, generating clean electricity, and transmitting diffuse light to improve building energy efficiency.

Developed in alignment with FAIR principles and Open Science practices, the DMP ensures how these heterogeneous datasets generated in SMARTWIN remain findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. To support long-term preservation and open access, an official Zenodo community has been created for hosting all material generated under SMARTWIN. Access to the community is:

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Organizations:

- 1- INSTITUTO DE ENERGÍA SOLAR - UNIVERSIDAD POLITÉCNICA DE MADRID.
- 2- FUNDACION IMDEA NANOCIENCIA

Contact: Víctor Bellón (victor.bellon@upm.es)

2. Funding

Funding organizativos: AGENCIA ESTATAL DE INVESTIGACIÓN (AEI)

Grants: Proyectos de Transición Ecológica y Transición Digital

Project: Design and demonstration of a translucent photovoltaic smart window for building-integrated photovoltaics (SMARTWIN).

3. License

License: CC-BY-4.0

Access Rights: Public

4. Templates

Descriptions

Template: AQUASERV | generic | template

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Types of data and usage

1.1.1 Data Types

SMARTWIN project could generate different types of data and outputs:

- Methodologies in *PDF*, *DOCX*, *TXT*, or *MD* formats.
- Characterization setups in *PDF*, *PNG*, *JPEG*, *TXT*, *INI*, or *DOCX* formats.
- Data on material characterization in *XML*, *CSV*, *XLSX*, *TXT*, or image data formats in *TIFF*, *PNG*, or *JPEG*.
- Digital twins or BIM models in *GH* (*Grasshopper*), *IDF* (*EnergyPlus*), *OSM* (*OpenStudio*), *IFC*, *RVT*, or *STEP* formats.
- Performance models in *PY*, *MATLAB files*, *JSON*, or *CSV* formats.
- Modelled hourly energy-generation datasets in *CSV* or *XLSX* formats.
- Software source code in Unicode text file format with arbitrary extensions depending on programming language (*C*, *H* or *PY files*)

1.1.2 Data Creation

The datasets in SMARTWIN will be created through:

- The design of optical, mechanical and electrical components and systems.
- The modeling of the optical, electrical, thermal or mechanical properties of components and systems.
- The definition of manufacturing procedures.
- The configuration of laboratory equipment and measurement benches.
- The experimental characterization of materials, components and systems.
- The results from building-energy simulations.
- Cost models, performance simulations and environmental impact assessments.

1.1.3 Published Data Re-use

Yes. The project may occasionally re-use public datasets necessary to support performance modelling, energy simulations, and building analyses. SMARTWIN could use solar irradiance databases (e.g. PVGIS).

2 FAIR Data Publication

2.1 Findable

2.1.1 Data Publication Repository

The datasets will be published in SMARTWIN community in Zenodo to ensure open access, preservation, and discoverability. Zenodo records are openly accessible and interoperable through REST API and OAI-PMH. Publications may be deposited in the UPM institutional repository (Archivo Digital), but all associated datasets will always be included in Zenodo.

Zenodo was selected as the main project's repository, because it supports many types of research outputs, links publications with datasets, allows creating a project community, assigns persistent DOIs, and offers reliable backup, versioning, and long-term preservation.

2.1.2 Metadata collection

All the following metadata will be completed when depositing datasets:

- Resource type: dataset, software, report, presentation, image, etc.
- Title: descriptive and unique.
- Authors: affiliation and ORCID number.
- Description: origin, methods, instrumentation, software, or parameters.
- Keywords: relevant technical terms.
- DOI: if not provided, it is automatically assigned by Zenodo.
- Funding information: including project reference (TED2021-130920B-C21), MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033, and European Union "Next Generation"/PRTR.
- Communities: SMARTWIN community.
- Access rights: supported by CC-BY 4.0.
- Version: version number.
- Related identifiers: include links to associated publications, software, or datasets.
- Format: file formats.
- Date: creation or publication date.
- Language: English.

Metadata will be completed according to the DataCite Metadata Schema used by Zenodo (creators, affiliations, resource types, keywords, funding, licenses). Zenodo stores metadata internally in JSON and exports them in DataCite, Dublin Core, and MARCXML, ensuring interoperability and harvesting.

2.2 Accessible

2.2.1 Repository

2.2.1.1 Open Access Data Repositories

Yes. Zenodo is a fully Open Access repository, where both data and metadata are publicly visible, searchable, and re-usable, ensuring maximum visibility and compliance with FAIR principles.

2.2.1.2 Persistent URLs and identifiers

Zenodo provides a DOI for every published dataset or output, ensuring permanent and citable access. In addition, all Zenodo records are accessible via a web interface, REST API, and OAI-PMH, supporting automated metadata harvesting.

2.2.2 Research Data

2.2.2.1 Data Publication Embargo

No embargo is expected to match the open science principles.

2.2.2.2 Restricted Data Usage

No. Openness is the default. All datasets will be openly available under CC-BY 4.0 license.

2.3 Interoperable

2.3.1 Open Data Formats

Yes, all datasets will be published in open standardized formats. Any data initially produced in a closed format will be converted before publication. Zenodo records are openly accessible and interoperable through REST API and OAI-PMH.

2.3.2 Vocabularies and Ontologies

Yes. We will use standardized lists of terms built into the DataCite metadata schema in Zenodo, for fields such as authors, affiliations, resource type, keywords, funding, and licenses. This ensures that the metadata is consistent and can be easily shared and understood by other repositories.

2.4 Re-useable (and reproducible)

2.4.1 Methods and Protocols

All datasets will be openly available under CC-BY 4.0 license, which permits anyone to use, share, and reproduce the data, if the original author is credited. Datasets and their metadata will be deposited in Zenodo as soon as they are generated without embargo or restrictions.

Each dataset will include provenance information and full documentation, such as methods, protocols, or procedures to ensure full reproducibility.

3 Other issues

Zenodo has a technical infrastructure that ensures data security and long-term preservation. Further details can be found at: <http://about.zenodo.org/infrastructure/>. Data stored in institutional repositories follows the specific policies of each institution.

In addition, roles and responsibilities have also been defined to guarantee proper data management:

- Data controllers: Instituto de Energía Solar - UPM and IMDEA, as each institution generates, processes, and manages different parts of the SMARTWIN datasets (optical measurements, materials characterization, simulations, prototype testing).
- Data Manager: Víctor Bellón (IES-UPM) will oversee data documentation, quality assurance, processing workflows, and updates to this DMP. Contact: victor.bellon@upm.es.
- Data processors: Researchers, laboratory technicians and project staff from UPM and IMDEA will collect, process and validate the datasets.

Regarding ethical aspects, SMARTWIN does not generate personal or sensitive data. No sensitive information will be deposited without prior agreement of the Consortium, following good practice by notifying any intended disclosure at least 15 days in advance.

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